

Synthesis of tri- and tetra-mannosides based on sequential one-pot three-component glycosylation reactions[†]

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Abstract : Expeditions syntheses of tri- and tetra-mannosides were carried out based on sequential one-pot glycosylation strategy. In both of these syntheses TMSOTf activated trichloroacetimidate, the first glycosyl donor, and inexpensive readily accessible trichloroisocyanuric acid (TCCA) in combination with catalytic amount of TMSOTf was used for activation of thioglycoside, the second glycosyl donor.

Keywords : Polysaccharide, glycosylation, TCCA, TMSOTf, sequential one pot.

Introduction

Lipopolysaccharides (LPSs) are highly abundant ingredients in the outer membrane of Gram-negative bacteria. Due to their abundance in outer bacterial membrane, the LPSs influence host-bacteria interactions like recognition, pathogenesis, symbiosis, adhesion, etc. They also play a pivotal role in bacterial cell stability, and prevent antibiotic and defense mechanism attacks¹.

Oligomannosides have long been established as biologically significant motifs. Several important bacteria contain (1→2)- α -linked di-, tri- or higher mannoside or modified mannoside units in their cell wall building blocks. HIV-1², *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*², *Vibrio cholerae*³ and *Escherichia coli* 09⁴ are among them. So, a lot of efforts have been directed towards synthesis of this class of saccharides as they exhibit key roles in immunochemical processes.

Owing to their immense potentiality in vaccination, 1,2-*trans* oligomannosides have been synthesized by various methods, e.g. stepwise glycosylation⁵, repetitive solid phase glycosylation⁶ and solution-phase automated synthesis⁷. Nonetheless, for environmental reasons, time and cost viability a one-pot multicomponent method is always desired. In continuation of our work in total synthesis of oligosaccharides⁸⁻¹⁰, we report a cost-effective and ex-

peditions chemical synthesis of (1→2)- α -linked tri- and tetra-mannoside units (Fig. 1) by a three-component one-pot strategy. Sequential one-pot¹¹ glycosylation technique was applied for these total syntheses utilizing TMSOTf for activation of the first trichloroacetimidate glycosyl donor and trichloroisocyanuric acid (TCCA, Fig. 2)-TMSOTf¹² combo catalyst for that of the second thioglycoside donor.

Fig. 1. Targeted tri- and tetra-mannosides.

Fig. 2. TCCA (trichloroisocyanuric acid).

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Results and discussion

The retrosynthesis of fully protected trisaccharide **3** and tetrasaccharide **4** resulted in four building blocks, mannose-derived monosaccharide units **5**, **6** and **7**, and mannose-based disaccharide building block **8** (Fig. 3). The first glycosyl donor **5** was armed with 2-OAc, 3,4,6-tri-OBn and α -trichloroacetimidate at the anomeric centre so that the 2-OAc group could make the donor more prone towards selective α -glycosylation via neighbouring group participation. The second mannose unit (**6**) would serve dual purpose in the total syntheses. At the first step it would play the role of a glycosyl acceptor and at the second step that of a donor. Tri-OBn-protected thioglycoside **6** having a 2-OH group proved to be well

equipped for this purpose. The reducing end monosaccharide **7** (for synthesis of **1**) and disaccharide **8** (for synthesis of **2**) had tri-/penta-OBn and anomeric OMe protection and a free hydroxyl group at C-2 and C-2' positions, respectively.

The carbohydrate moieties **7**^{8,10} and **11**^{8,10} were prepared via the 1,2-orthoester (**10**)^{8,10} from commercially available D-mannose following reported methods (Scheme 1). Zemplén deacetylation¹³ of **11** afforded the monosaccharide **6**¹⁴ in quantitative yield. Hydrolysis¹⁵ of **11** by TCCA in aqueous (CH₃)₂CO furnished 2-*O*-acetyl-3,4,6-tri-*O*-benzyl-D-mannopyranose (**12**)¹⁶ in 85% yield. Treatment of this product with trichloroacetonitrile and DBU in dry CH₂Cl₂ provided the acetimidate donor **5**¹⁶ in 91% yield.

Fig. 3. Retrosynthetic analysis of tri- and tetra-mannoside.

Scheme 1. Reagents and conditions : (a) NaOMe, MeOH, rt, 2 h; (b) TCCA, (CH₃)₂CO.H₂O, 0 °C; (c) CCl₃CN, DBU, CH₂Cl₂, -5 °C; (d) TMSOTf, -5 °C to rt.

After preparing the monosaccharide building blocks, the disaccharide unit **13**^{5,8,10} was prepared through glycosylation of **5** and **7** in 92% yield, using TMSOTf. Deacetylation of **13** furnished disaccharide acceptor **8**^{5,8,10} in quantitative yield.

After being equipped with all these building blocks we turned our attention to the synthesis of the targeted mannosides **1** and **2** applying sequential one-pot glycosylation strategy (Scheme 2). Trichloroacetimidate donor **5** and thio acceptor **6** were reacted with 20 mol% TMSOTf at $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After 10 min clean conversion toward the corresponding disaccharide was observed by TLC. In the same reaction vessel non-reducing acceptor **7** was then added along with 1 equiv. of TCCA and 10 mol% TMSOTf at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After the addition, reaction temperature was quickly raised to room temperature. After 15

min TLC showed full conversion to the fully protected trisaccharide. The crude product was purified by flash chromatography, providing 84% pure trimannoside derivative **3**¹⁷. Zémplen deacetylation¹³ and global debenzoylation under catalytic hydrogenation conditions finally furnished the corresponding fully deprotected trisaccharide as its methyl glycoside (**1**)¹⁷

The desired tetrasaccharide (**2**) was prepared (Scheme 2) following the same protocol. Common intermediate disaccharide, resulting in the first step of trisaccharide **1** synthesis, was generated *in situ* in a similar way. After that, disaccharide acceptor **8**, 1 equiv. TCCA and 10 mol% TMSOTf were added to the reaction mass at $0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the same reaction vessel. Temperature was increased immediately after the addition. TLC indicated completion of the reaction after 20 min. The tetrasaccharide

Scheme 2. Reagents and conditions : (a) TMSOTf, CH_2Cl_2 , $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$; (b) TCCA, $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to rt; (c) (i) NaOMe (0.05 M), MeOH, rt; (ii) H_2 , Pd/C, MeOH-EtOAc, rt.

derivative **4**⁶ was obtained in 80% yield after purification of the crude product by flash column chromatography. Zémpfen deacetylation and global debenzoylation under catalytic hydrogenation conditions finally furnished the corresponding tetrasaccharide as its methyl glycoside (**2**).

Conclusion

In summary, we have successfully synthesized a tri- and a tetra-mannoside in high yields following sequential one-pot glycosylation technique. This method is expeditious, and the reagent TCCA is an inexpensive, easily available, green one. To our belief, this high yielding process has potential for the rapid synthesis of various other useful oligosaccharide motifs.

Experimental

NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DPX 300 NMR spectrometer operating at 300 MHz and 75 MHz for ¹H and ¹³C NMR, respectively in CDCl₃. HRMS data were recorded on a Q-tof-Micro mass spectrometer by electron spray ionization method. Specific rotations were measured on a Jasco J-815 spectrometer.

2-O-Acetyl-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl trichloroacetimidate (**5**)¹⁶ :

A suspension of **11** (1.0 g, 1.6 mmol) and TCCA¹⁵ (371.86 mg, 1 equiv.) in (CH₃)₂CO.H₂O (4 : 1) was kept on stirring at 0 °C for 30 min. After reaction completion (indicated by TLC) (CH₃)₂CO was evaporated *in vacuo* and the resulting mass was diluted with CH₂Cl₂ (15 mL). The solution was washed subsequently with saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ (200 mL) and water. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated. The residue was filtered through column on silica gel (eluent : Pet ether/EtOAc, 4 : 1) to afford *2-O-acetyl-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl-D-mannopyranose* **12**¹⁶ (721 mg, 85%) as white foam. To a suspension of **12** (800 mg, 1.5 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂ (10 mL), trichloroacetonitrile (0.23 mL, 2.25 mmol) and DBU (0.04 mL, 0.3 mmol) were added dropwise subsequently at -5 °C. After completion of reaction, CH₂Cl₂ was removed in rotary evaporator. The sticky brown mass was chromatographed on 60–120 mesh silica gel (eluent : Pet ether/EtOAc, 9 : 1) to get pure compound **5** as colorless syrup (920 mg, 91%); [α]_D²⁵ +30.1° (*c* 1.2, CHCl₃); lit.¹⁶ [α]_D +36.3° (*c* 0.9, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.20 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.72 (1H, m), 3.85 (1H, dd, *J* 3.3, 11.1 Hz),

4.00–4.06 (3H, m), 4.51 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 4.54 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz), 4.58 (1H, d, *J* 11.2 Hz), 4.69 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz), 4.74 (1H, d, *J* 11.3 Hz), 4.88 (1H, d, *J* 10.6 Hz), 5.51 (1H, s), 6.31 (1H, d, *J* 1.7 Hz, H₁), 7.17–7.20 (2H, m, ArH), 7.29–7.37 (13H, m, ArH), 8.68 (1H, s, NH). Data were in agreement with those reported in the literature¹⁶.

Phenyl 3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl-1-thio- α -D-mannopyranoside (**6**)¹⁴ :

To a solution of **11** (1.0 g, 1.6 mmol) in dry MeOH (10 mL) 1 (*M*) methanolic NaOMe (0.2 mL) solution was added, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then neutralized with Amberlite-120(H⁺) and filtered. The resin was washed with MeOH, and the combined filtrates were concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent : Pet ether/EtOAc, 5 : 1) to give glassy syrupy product (0.92 g, 99%); [α]_D²⁵ +169.1° (*c* 1.2, CHCl₃); lit.¹⁴ [α]_D +182.5° (*c* 1.26, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.69 (1H, m), 3.81 (1H, dd, *J* 4.5, 10.9 Hz), 3.87–3.3.98 (2H, m), 4.26–4.33 (2H, m), 4.47 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz), 4.54 (1H, d, *J* 10.8 Hz), 4.63 (1H, d, *J* 12.0 Hz), 4.73 (2H, s), 4.85 (1H, d, *J* 10.8 Hz), 5.62 (1H, s), 7.22–7.38 (18H, m, ArH), 7.46–7.48 (2H, m, ArH). Data were in agreement with those reported in the literature¹⁴.

Methyl 2-O-acetyl-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranoside (**13**)^{5,8,10} :

Compound **5** (255.0 mg, 0.38 mmol) and compound **7** (145.8 mg, 0.31 mmol) was dissolved in dry CH₂Cl₂ (10 mL) and the mixture was stirred under Ar for 30 min with powdered 4 Å MS. TMSOTf (17.0 μ L, 0.09 mmol) was added to the reaction mixture, and it was allowed to stir for 30 min at -5 °C. The reaction mixture was then filtered through Celite bed, and the residue was washed with CH₂Cl₂ (2 \times 10 mL). The combined filtrate was washed with saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ and water. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated to a syrupy product. The residue was purified by flash column chromatography (eluent : Pet ether/EtOAc, 4 : 1) to afford the title compound **13** as colorless syrup (271 mg, 92%); [α]_D²⁵ +21.6° (*c* 1.8, CHCl₃); lit.⁵ [α]_D +19.0° (*c* 1.8, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.12 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.26 (3H, s, OCH₃),

3.69–3.3.89 (8H, m), 3.9–4.01 (3H, m), 4.39–4.48 (3H, m), 4.51–4.58 (3H, m), 4.65–4.68 (5H, m), 4.78–4.88 (3H, m), 5.09 (1H, bs), 5.55 (1H, m), 7.15–7.21 (5H, m, ArH), 7.27–7.33 (25H, m, ArH). Data were in agreement with those reported in the literature^{5,8,10}.

Methyl 3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranoside (8)^{5,8,10} :

To a stirred solution of **13** (300.0 mg, 0.31 mmol) in dry MeOH (9 mL) was added 1 (*M*) methanolic NaOMe (0.5 mL) solution, and the reaction mixture was stirred for 5 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then neutralized with Amberlite-120(H⁺) and filtered. The resin was washed with MeOH, and the combined filtrates were concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (eluent : Pet ether/EtOAc, 5 : 1) to give glassy syrupy product (284.0 mg, 99%); [α]_D²⁵ +25.0° (*c* 1.2, CHCl₃); lit.⁵ [α]_D +26.8° (*c* 1.7, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 3.25 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.70–3.74 (4H, m), 3.78–3.81 (2H, m), 3.84 (1H, d, *J* 2.9 Hz), 3.87 (1H, d, *J* 2.8 Hz), 3.90 (1H, d, *J* 2.7 Hz), 3.95 (1H, m), 4.04 (1H, m), 4.14 (1H, m), 4.50 (1H, d, *J* 5.1 Hz), 4.53 (1H, apparent t, *J* 2.3, 3.6 Hz), 4.57–4.59 (1H, d, *J* 5.0 Hz), 4.62 (1H, s), 4.66–4.73 (3H, m), 4.81–4.87 (3H, m), 5.16 (1H, m), 7.18–7.36 (30H, m, ArH). Data were in agreement with those reported in the literature^{5,8,10}.

*Methyl 2-O-acetyl-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranoside (3)*¹⁷ :

To a solution of **5** (115.0 mg, 0.17 mmol) and **6** (90.3 mg, 0.16 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂, activated 4 Å MS was added and it was kept on stirring under Ar for 30 min. Then the reaction mixture was cooled to –5 °C and catalytic amount of TMSOTf (5.6 μ L, 0.03 mmol) was added to it via a micro syringe. After 10 min complete conversion towards the expected dimer was observed. Compound **7** (64.0 mg, 0.14 mmol), TCCA (32.5 mg, 0.14 mmol) and TMSOTf (2.8 μ L, 0.015 mmol) were added to the same vessel at –5 °C. After the addition, reaction temperature was raised quickly to room temperature. The second step of the reaction was completed after 15 min (indicated by TLC). It was then filtered through Celite bed, and the residue was washed with CH₂Cl₂ (2 \times 10 mL). The combined filtrate was washed with saturated aqueous NaHCO₃ and water. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and concentrated to a syrupy

product. The residue was purified by flash column chromatography (eluent : Pet ether/EtOAc, 4 : 1) to afford the title compound **3** as colorless syrup (170.3 mg, 84%); [α]_D²⁵ +10.2° (*c* 1.5, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 2.14 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.23 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.53 (1H, d, *J* 10.5 Hz), 3.65–3.69 (2H, m), 3.72–3.79 (5H, m), 3.81–3.84 (2H, d, *J* 9.9 Hz), 3.87–3.93 (4H, m), 3.95–3.99 (2H, m), 4.11 (1H, m), 4.32 (1H, d, *J* 12.1 Hz), 4.41–4.47 (2H, m), 4.51–4.55 (4H, m), 4.58–4.59 (4H, m), 4.63–4.67 (3H, m), 4.70 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz), 4.81–4.87 (4H, m), 5.06 (1H, bs), 5.21 (1H, bs), 5.55 (1H, m), 7.15–7.36 (45H, m, ArH); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 21.2 (COCH₃), 54.7 (OCH₃), 68.8, 69.6, 71.7, 71.9, 72.1, 72.2, 73.3, 73.4, 74.3, 74.9, 75.0, 75.1, 78.1, 79.3, 79.5, 99.4, 99.8, 100.6, 127.4, 127.5, 127.6, 127.7, 127.8, 127.9, 128.0, 128.16, 128.23, 128.3, 128.4, 138.1, 138.2, 138.4, 138.5, 138.6, 170.1 (COCH₃). Data were in agreement with those reported in the literature¹⁷.

*Methyl α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- α -D-mannopyranoside (1)*¹⁷ :

2-OAc Protection of trisaccharide **3** (50 mg, 0.034 mmol) was removed by applying Zémplén deacetylation method. Then the resulting compound was treated with 10% Pd/C (70 mg) in MeOH-EtOAc (3 : 1, 3 mL) and kept on stirring under the atmosphere of H₂ for 24 h. The reaction mixture was filtered through Celite bed, and the residue was washed with MeOH (3 \times 10 mL). The combined filtrate and washings was concentrated under reduced pressure. The product was passed through Celite bed to give **1** (16 mg, 91%); [α]_D²⁵ +75.2° (*c* 1.5, H₂O); ¹H NMR (300 MHz, D₂O) : δ 3.27 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.50–3.55 (2H, m), 3.62–3.64 (2H, m), 3.75–3.80 (4H, m), 3.95 (1H, d, *J* 11.0 Hz), 4.86 (1H, bs), 4.91 (1H, bs), 5.17 (1H, bs); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, D₂O) : δ 54.9 (OCH₃), 60.9, 61.1, 66.8, 67.0, 67.1, 70.0, 70.2, 70.3, 72.6, 73.2, 78.5, 78.7, 99.3, 100.6, 102.2. Data were in agreement with those reported in the literature¹⁷.

*Methyl 2-O-acetyl-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)-3,4,6-tri-O-benzyl- α -D-mannopyranoside (4)*⁶ :

To a solution of **5** (72.0 mg, 0.11 mmol) and **6** (56.5 mg, 0.10 mmol) in dry CH₂Cl₂, activated 4 Å MS was added and it was kept on stirring under Ar for 30 min. Then the reaction mixture was cooled to –5 °C and cata-

lytic amount of TMSOTf (3.6 μ L, 0.02 mmol) was added to it via a micro syringe. After 10 min complete conversion towards the expected dimer was observed. Compound **8** (82.49 mg, 0.09 mmol), TCCA (20.92 mg, 0.09 mmol) and TMSOTf (1.8 μ L, 0.01 mmol) was added to the same vessel at -5 $^{\circ}$ C. After the addition, reaction temperature was raised quickly to room temperature. The second step of the reaction was completed after 20 min (indicated by TLC). It was then filtered through Celite bed, and the residue was washed with CH_2Cl_2 (2×10 mL). The combined filtrate was washed with saturated aqueous NaHCO_3 and water. The organic layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and concentrated to a syrupy product. The residue was purified by flash column chromatography (eluent : Pet ether/EtOAc, 4 : 1) to afford the title compound **4** as colorless syrup (136.77 mg, 80%); $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} + 12.2$ $^{\circ}$ C (c 1.5, CHCl_3); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 2.13 (3H, s, COCH_3), 3.21 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.43–3.53 (2H, m), 3.61–3.66 (3H, m), 3.69–3.79 (7H, m), 3.83–4.00 (9H, m), 4.10–4.22 (4H, m), 4.31–4.38 (3H, m), 4.42–4.50 (8H, m), 4.52–4.56 (5H, m), 4.59–4.69 (5H, m), 4.75–4.86 (5H, m), 5.04 (1H, s), 5.20 (1H, m), 5.30 (1H, s), 5.53 (1H, m), 6.97–7.54 (60H, m, ArH); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 21.1 (COCH_3), 54.6 (OCH_3), 68.7, 69.4, 71.5, 71.7, 71.9, 72.2, 72.7, 73.26, 73.34, 74.3, 74.8, 75.0, 75.2, 75.4, 77.57, 77.63, 78.3, 79.4, 99.4, 99.7, 100.7, 101.0, 127.46, 127.52, 127.66, 127.73, 127.8, 128.0, 128.1, 128.3, 128.4, 128.5, 138.1, 138.2, 138.3, 138.4, 138.5, 170.1 (COCH_3).

*Methyl α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- α -D-mannopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 2)- α -D-mannopyranoside (**2**) :*

2-OAc protection of tetrasaccharide **4** (60 mg, 0.03 mmol) was removed by applying Zémpfen deacetylation method. Then the resulting compound was treated with 10% Pd/C (70 mg) in MeOH-EtOAc (3 : 1, 3 mL) and kept on stirring under the atmosphere of H_2 for 24 h. The reaction mixture was filtered through Celite bed, and the residue was washed with MeOH (3×10 mL). The combined filtrate and washings was concentrated under reduced pressure. The product was passed through Celite bed to give **2** (18.89 mg, 90%); $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} + 85.7^{\circ}$ (c 1.5, H_2O); ^1H NMR (300 MHz, D_2O) : δ 3.26 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.47–3.54 (4H, m), 3.57–3.63 (8H, m), 3.68–3.77 (5H, m), 3.79–3.83 (3H, m), 3.93–3.95 (1H, m), 4.68 (1H, bs, merged with HOD peak), 4.85 (1H, bs), 4.90 (1H,

bs), 5.16 (1H, bs); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, D_2O) : δ 54.7 (OCH_3), 60.8, 60.0, 66.7, 66.8, 67.0, 69.9, 70.1, 70.2, 72.5, 73.1, 78.4, 78.7, 99.2 (2C), 100.5, 102.1.

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